

A Comparative Study of In-Person and App-Based DBT: Implications for Executive Functioning in Borderline Personality Disorder

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ABSTRACT

This study examined whether Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT) improves Executive Functioning in patients with Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD), and compared outcomes between traditional in-person treatment and a digital format delivered via an app. For the digital arm, we developed Life+, a bespoke e-mental health application designed to deliver DBT protocols. A total of 96 participants ($M = 22.34$; $SD = 2.67$; ages 18–29) were recruited by Simple Random Sampling from a public university in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and randomly assigned to either the in-person DBT group ($n = 48$) or Life+ app group ($n = 48$). BPD symptoms were screened with the McLean Screening Instrument, and Executive Functioning was measured using BRIEF-A. Both groups completed a 12-week DBT program and were re-assessed after a three-month follow-up to examine the durability of effects. Data was analyzed using Paired & Independent t-Test; descriptive statistics, & Repeated-Measures ANOVA; within-subject effect sizes were computed for the paired comparisons. Results indicated a statistically significant improvement in Executive Functioning within the control group ($p < .001$), whereas the experimental group demonstrated comparatively smaller, yet significant improvements ($p < .05$). Findings from repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a marked reduction in BPD symptoms in the control group at both post-test and follow-up assessments. Conversely, the experimental group exhibited reductions in BPD symptoms at posttest but demonstrated a slight symptom increase at follow-up.

Overall, findings confirm that in person DBT is more efficient in minimizing BPD symptomatology and enhancing Executive Functioning compared to app-based DBT delivery. Nevertheless, the Life+ application demonstrated efficacy in reducing BPD symptoms and enhancing distress tolerance, though to a lesser degree. These results underscore the potential benefit of a hybrid model that integrates e-mental health tools with traditional, in-person therapy to optimize clinical outcomes and ensure long-term treatment gains.

KEYWORDS

Executive Functioning, Life+ App, Borderline Personality Disorder, McLean Screening Instrument, BRIEF-A.

1. Introduction

Borderline Personality Disorder

As per DSM-5, the identification of Borderline Personality Disorder consist of five signs out of nine. These signs consist of intentional efforts to escape desertion, unstable relationships & self-image, impulsivity, anger, affective-instability, suicidal behavior, chronic emptiness, and dissociative symptoms. (Artioli, 2022). Similarly, Beatson et al. (2019) describe BPD as a personality disorder characterized by these emotional, cognitive, and behavioral disturbances.

BPD typically emerges during adolescence and may persist into adulthood (Thompson et al., 2018). However, research also indicates that BPD can be present in older adults,

challenging the notion that it is exclusively a disorder of early adulthood (Ouwens et al., 2022).

The development of BPD is best understood through a biopsychosocial framework, which considers genetic, neurobiological, psychological, and environmental influences that interact to shape its onset and course (Winsper, 2018). The Biopsychosocial Model posits that BPD results from a combination of biological vulnerabilities (e.g., genetic predisposition, temperament, prenatal factors), invalidating caregiving environments, and maladaptive interpersonal interactions.

Genetic factors are estimated to account for approximately 35–65% of the risk for BPD (Amad, 2014; Skoglund et al., 2021). Children of mothers with BPD are more likely to display BPD-related symptoms, with studies reporting low to

modest magnitude (Steele et al., 2019; Reinelt et al., 2013). Similarly, experiences of maltreatment, when combined with hereditary predispositions, significantly enhance the likelihood of developing full-syndrome BPD (Wilson et al., 2021). Moreover, individuals with a full sibling diagnosed with BPD have nearly a fivefold increased risk of developing the disorder themselves (Skoglund et al., 2021).

Executive Functioning and Borderline Personality Disorder

Executive Functioning are the mental skills that control thoughts, emotions, and actions, including decision-making, working memory, planning, & the ability to respond adaptively to rewards and challenges (Pizzie et al., 2020). Research suggests that patients with BPD often display neurological soft sig—subtle neurodevelopmental abnormalities—that are associated with chronic feelings of emptiness, impaired awareness of consequences, sensory-perceptual difficulties, attention deficits, and impulsivity (Khoweiled et al., 2021). These neurological features indicate that BPD is associated with significant cognitive impairments, including disrupted attention, psychomotor functioning, and deficits in neuropsychological domains such as theory of mind and memory (Andrews et al., 2020).

Research indicates that non-planning impulsivity is a hitherto understudied mechanism connecting BPD and suicidality. Impulsivity, a fundamental characteristic of BPD, has been demonstrated to predict the frequency of suicide attempts (Andrews et al., 2020). Compared to non-BPD groups, those with BPD are more likely to exhibit attention-related issues, and cognitive deficiencies are closely linked to more general psychopathology (Thomsen et al., 2017; Unoka & Richman, 2016). In addition to being a defining feature of BPD, cognitive impairment is also a major focus for treatment, with programs increasingly being developed to address executive dysfunction in this demographic (Belvederi Murri et al., 2021).

E-Mental Health Applications and Dialectical Behavior Therapy

Dialectical Behavior Therapy is generally accepted as gold standard for treating BPD & evidence-based treatment is

essential for personality disorders (Linehan, 1993). However, the expense, stigma associated with mental health care, availability of therapists & practical obstacles like travel continue to restrict access to traditional psychotherapy (Mohr & Rosén, 2017).

E-mental health applications—digital tools delivered via smartphones or the internet—have surfaced as an emerging way to address these barriers. Such tools can enhance cost-effectiveness (Donker et al., 2015), expand access to treatment options (Raney et al., 2017), reduce mental health stigma (Kim et al., 2023), and provide individualized interventions tailored to a patient's needs and context (Perna et al., 2018). Mobile DBT applications are especially valuable in contexts where access to trained therapists is limited. The usability and content of these applications are among their most beneficial features (Wilks et al., 2021).

Despite their potential research on DBT, mobile applications remains limited. A scientific review by Ilagan et al. (2020) found only three studies that had tested app-based DBT interventions. In a pilot study of 16 participants, Rizvi et al. (2020) reported that non-suicidal self-injury decreased more in those using DBT apps compared to those receiving standard DBT alone. Other studies have focused on the design, usability, and engagement with e-mental health applications, but further research is needed to establish their efficacy (Schroeder et al., 2020).

Comparing in person DBT and App-Based DBT

This research aimed to directly compare the efficacy of DBT administered in-person with DBT delivered through an e-mental health application. Whitchurch et al. (2022), in a qualitative investigation, explored patient experiences of in-person and online DBT, identifying five key themes: (a) learning processes, (b) transition from isolation to community, (c) physical and environmental factors, (d) improvements in daily functioning, and (e) DBT's lasting impact. Their findings revealed that participants appreciated comfort & flexibility of on-line treatment but valued the sense of connection and community fostered in in person sessions.

During Covid-19 pandemic, the widespread adoption of teletherapy demonstrated that DBT could be delivered

effectively in a virtual format without compromising treatment outcomes (Wind et al., 2020). A survey by Chenneville and Schwartz-Mette (2020) reported that 76% of clinicians transitioned to teletherapy during this period, further underscoring the feasibility of online delivery. Nevertheless, research on online DBT remains limited, with Hyland et al. (2022) being among the few to investigate its outcomes systematically.

Some challenges have been reported, particularly regarding therapeutic alliance, a key determinant of treatment success. Online formats may hinder rapport-building due to reduced ability to read nonverbal cues, while patients may experience screen fatigue (Beattie et al., 2009; Geller, 2023). Given that DBT relies heavily on a strong therapeutic alliance—where

therapists serve as both instructors and validators—this limitation may affect treatment outcomes (Linehan, 1993; Cameron et al., 2018).

In Pakistan, there is limited data on the economic burden of BPD. Despite available treatment guidelines, implementation remains inconsistent (Hastrup et al., 2019). Psychotherapy has been proven to be the main element of the treatment (Simonsen et al., 2019), yet treatment resistance remains a significant challenge, often resulting in severe clinical consequences. This research seeks to fill this area by exploring alternative/complementary modes of therapy delivery that may overcome individual differences contributing to treatment resistance.

Conceptual Framework

Objectives

1. To evaluate the change in executive functioning scores after treatment with DBT & the Life+ application.
2. To analyze the differential change in BPD symptom scores across three measurement occasions (Post-test; Pre-test & Follow-up) between two intervention groups: standard DBT & the e-mental health application.
3. To compare the overall efficacy of DBT delivered in person with DBT delivered via the e - mental health application.

Hypotheses

1. After receiving a combined DBT and e-mental health application intervention, people with BPD will reveal a statistically significant change in their executive functioning scores in Pre-to – Post -Test.
2. Behavior Regulation Index & Metacognition Index scores of BRIEF-A will differ statistically significantly between BPD patients before and after DBT and the e-mental health application are administered.
3. Compared to the experimental group (which received DBT via the Life+ app), patients in the Control Group will reflect a larger decline in BPD symptom levels throughout Pre-Test; Post-Test & Follow-up assessments.
4. The effectiveness of treatment will differ significantly between DBT administered in-person and DBT administered via

2. Method

The present study employed an experimental research design to check the comparative efficacy of In-person DBT and DBT administered via an e-mental health application. This section outlines the study's data collection procedures, participant characteristics, ethical considerations, treatment protocols, and study procedures.

Participants and Sample Size

Participants were recruited from the student population of Islamia College, Peshawar, using simple random sampling.

Enrollment data were obtained Admission and Academics & Research Offices. Total 5,223 students (aged 18 – 29 years) were approached across twenty one academic departments from March to June, 2022. Four departments without enrolled students were excluded. The study included students from BS, MA/MSc, MPhil programs, and the Constituent College.

To estimate prevalence, the ScaleX calculator was used, with an estimated Prevalence Rate of 62%. This yielded a required sample size of 578 participants, allowing for absolute - precision of $\pm 4\%$ at a 95 % CI, and accounting for a 2% Attrition Rate. Based on this sample, the anticipated CI was 58–65%.

186 students met the screening cutoff (score ≥ 7) out of 578 students identified via MacLean Screening Instrument for Borderline Personality Disorder (MSI - BPD). For randomization into treatment conditions, a more stringent cutoff (score ≥ 8) was applied. Using RaoSoft sample size calculations, a final sample of 96 participants was selected. Block randomization was employed to ensure equal group sizes, resulting in 48 participants in Control Group (In person DBT) and 48 in the Experimental Group (DBT through Life+ app).

Inclusion Criteria

- Participants scoring ≥ 7 on the MacLean Screening Instrument for BPD.
- Age range of 18–29 years.
- Fluency in the language of intervention and assessment materials.
- Completion of 24 DBT sessions (45–60 minutes each) as part of the intervention protocol.

Exclusion Criteria

- Those who received non-DBT therapy in the three months before the study were excluded.
- Participants undergoing DBT-based phone coaching were excluded in the study.

- Patients with current substance dependence (e.g., alcohol or drug abuse) were excluded, as these conditions could interfere with treatment adherence.
- Those with serious cognitive impairments were not included because they might not fully benefit from DBT.
- Participants with language-barriers were excluded because that could affect comprehension or engagement in therapy.

Randomization and Blinding

A single-blinded randomization procedure was applied to assign participants to the two intervention groups. Randomization was conducted to ensure balance between the groups while maintaining allocation concealment. Participants were unaware of their group assignments throughout the study to minimize expectancy effects and response bias.

Instruments

Demographic Questionnaire.

A structured demographic sheet was used to collect information about patients like gender; age; marital status; socioeconomic status; psychological history; medical history; childhood trauma; and parental relationship patterns.

MSI-BPD

McLean Screening Instrument for Borderline Personality Disorder, introduced by Zanarini and colleagues in 2003, is a brief 10-item Self-Report checklist used to screen for BPD symptoms. Each item is scored dichotomously (0 = no, 1 = yes), so scores varies from 0 to 10; a score of 7 or higher typically indicates probable BPD and suggests further clinical assessment.

BRIEF-A

The Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function — Adult Version (Roth, Isquith, & Gioia, 2005); is a 75-Items Self-Report Instrument which evaluates adult Executive Functioning among nine clinical domains (Self-Monitor;

Working Memory Shift; Emotional Control; Inhibit; Task Monitor; Initiate; Plan/Organize; & Organization of Material). Respondents rate every sentence on a 3 - Point Scale (1 = never, 2 = sometimes, 3 = often). BRIEF-A presented good Internal Consistency (overall indices often report Cronbach's α in the mid-.90s), and higher total scores reflect greater executive dysfunction — therefore, reductions in scores from Pre - to- Post Treatment indicate improvement

Intervention

In-person DBT (Control Group)

Patients in Control Group attended 24 DBT sessions, each lasting 45–60 minutes, conducted by trained therapists. Sessions followed the standard DBT protocol outlined by Linehan (1993), including modules on Emotion Regulations; Distress Tolerance; Interpersonal Effectiveness; & Mindfulness.

E-Mental Health App (Experimental Group)

The experimental group received DBT via a custom-developed e-mental health application. The app content was adapted from the DBT manual by Marsha Linehan and culturally tailored before deployment. Written materials, audio, and video content were reviewed for appropriateness and integrated into the app after obtaining permission from the publisher.

The app contained 24 sequentially locked sessions, requiring completion of each session (including homework and feedback) before unlocking the next. Participants were guided through three main menu sections:

1. **Skill Training Programs:** Written notes, audio-visual content, and structured exercises for DBT modules.
2. **Structure of Mind:** Visual and explanatory content describing DBT concepts.
3. **Session Details and Feedback:** Space for participants to submit homework and record reflections, enabling therapist monitoring.

Participants who failed to complete the first session or submit required feedback/homework were considered discontinued and denied access to remaining sessions.

3. Results

Table 1

Sociodemographic characteristics of the Participants (N=578).

Baseline-Characteristics	N	%
Gender		
Male	252	43
Female	326	56
SES	-	-
20,000-30,000	58	10
40,000-50,000	101	17
60,000-70,000	202	34
70,000 and above	216	37
Prevalence of Borderline Personality Disorder	-	-
Yes	186	32
Gender-based Prevalence Female	98	17
Male	88	15
No	392	67
Age	-	-
18-21	365	63
22-25	209	36
26-29	3	0.5
Comorbidities		
No Depression	410	70
Depression	168	29
No Anxiety	500	86
Anxiety	78	13
Psychotropic Drugs		
No Psychotropic Drugs	551	95
Taking Psychotropic Drugs	27	4

Note: out of 578 participants 88 male (15%) diagnosed with Borderline Personality Disorder, therefore, 98 Females (17%) females were identified with BPD.

Table 2

Baseline comparison between DBT In-person Group and Life+ App Group on demographic variables (N=82)

Demographic Variables	DBT face to face group Mean (SD)	Life + App group Mean (SD)
Gender		
Male	13(65.9%)	11 (27.5%)
Female	29 (72.5%)	29 (72.5.5%)
Age		
18-21 years	12(28.6%)	19 (47.5%)
22-25 years	28 (66.7%)	20 (50.0%)
26-29 years	2 (4.8%)	1(2.5%)
Education		
F.Sc	3(7.1%)	2(5.0%)
BS	20(47.6%)	29(72.5%)
MSc/MA	16(38.1)	8(20.0%)
MPhil	4(7.1%)	1(2.5%)
Family Monthly income		
20,000 to 30,000	7 (16.7%)	8 (20.0%)
40,000 to 50,000	13 (31.0%)	5 (12.5%)
60,000 to 70,000	14 (33.3%)	12 (30.0%)
70,000 and above	8 (19.0%)	15 (37.5%)
Family structure		
Joint	24 (57.1%)	15 (37.5%)
Nuclear	18 (42.9%)	25(62.5%)

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation for Study Variables BRIEF-A (N=42)

Variables	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
BPD. Pa	42	8.31	.975	1											
Inh	42	17.64	3.70	.327**	1										
Shi	42	13.36	1.96	.477**	.581**	1									
EC	42	20.62	5.18	.471**	.497**	.611**	1								
SM	42	18.43	5.31	.442**	.586**	.599**	.538*	1							
Init	42	16.60	2.49	.301*	.500**	.631**	.621*	.666**	1						
WM	42	16.86	2.94	.362**	.534**	.492**	.411*	.617**	.622*	1					
PO	42	20.40	3.27	.506**	.595**	.621**	.550*	.655**	.674*	.532**	1				
TM	42	14.79	1.88	.302*	.216	.337*	.117	.562**	.245	.576**	.165	1			
OM	42	18.10	3.14	.275*	.078	.180	-.008	.366**	.109	.294	.244	.636**	1		
BRI	42	70.04	12.13	.323**	.554**	.556**	.607*	.697**	.572*	.562**	.607**	.435**	.218	1	
MI	42	86.73	9.27	.542**	.651**	.645**	.447*	.510**	.553*	.655**	.666**	.467**	.402**	.585*	1

Inh = Inhibit; Shi = Shift; BPD = Borderline Personality Disorder; SM = Self-Monitor; EC = Emotional Control; WM = Working Memory; Init = Initiate; PO = Plan Organize; PO = Plan Organize; OM = Organization of Material; TM = Task Monitor; BR = Behavior Regulation Index; MI = Metacognitive Index.

^a 0 = BPD not present; 1 = BPD present

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

A Pearson correlation analysis shows a higher positive link between Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) symptom severity and overall executive dysfunction. Specifically, BPD symptoms showed significant positive correlations with most BRIEF-A subscales and composite indices (e.g., MI: $r = .542$, $p < .01$; PO: $r = .506$, $p < .01$), with the exception of the Shift subscale, which showed a significant negative relationship ($r = -.477$, $p < .01$). This indicates that higher BPD symptomatology is generally associated with greater reported difficulties in executive functioning.

Table 4

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention & Post - Intervention on EF among BPD (N=42)

	Pre-Intervention		Post Intervention		t (41)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Inh	16.07	3.30	9.86	1.37	11.61	<.001	1.79
Shi	12.88	1.75	8.88	2.03	9.81	<.001	1.52
EC	20.81	4.16	12.45	1.75	14.13	<.001	2.18
SM	13.60	2.01	8.74	2.20	10.57	<.001	1.63

Note: Shi = Shift; Inh = Inhibit; SM = Self – Monitor; EC = Emotional Control.
***p<.001.

Paired-samples t tests assessed DBT effects across executive-function domains. Results showed large, significant pre→post reductions in executive dysfunction. Therefore, DBT has substantial effect in improving overall executive functioning.

Table 5

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention and Post - Intervention on EF (Inhibit; Plan Organize; Task Monitor; Working Memory; Organization of Material) among BPD (N=42)

W	17.10	10.02	12.6	<.00	1.95
M	2.91	1.82	4	1	
PO	19.12	12.05	11.5	<.00	1.78
	3.51	2.71	3	1	
TM	12.48	7.43	11.8	<.00	1.83
	2.43	1.29	6	1	
OM	15.33	10.05	10.7	<.00	1.66
	2.84	1.80	9	1	

Note: WM = Working Memory; PO = Plan Organize; Init = Initiate; OM = Organization of Material; OM = Organization of Material.TM = Task Monitor.
***p<.001.

	Pre-Intervention	Post-Intervention	t (39)	P	Cohen's d
	M SD	M SD			
Init	16.31 2.54	9.26 2.04	14.88	<.001	2.30

Paired-samples t tests indicated that DBT produced statistically significant improvements across all assessed executive-function domains, with large effect sizes.

Table 6

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention and Post - Intervention on Behavioral Regulation Index and Metacognition Index among BPD (N=42)

	Pre-Intervention		Post Intervention		t (39)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
BRI	63.35	8.37	49.19	4.07	18.70	<.001	1.80
MI	80.61	10.32	39.92	5.27	18.68	<.001	3.58

BRI = Behavioral Regulation Index; MI = Metacognition Index.
***p<.001.

EC	42	23.10	3.47	.314*	.565**	.577**	1									
SM	42	12.51	2.45	.242*	.512**	.588**	.414**	1								
Init	42	16.33	3.59	.394*	.694**	.657**	.528**	.615**	1							
WM	42	17.44	3.17	.359*	.579**	.628**	.695**	.671**	.795**	1						
PO	42	19.82	3.75	.392*	.693**	.671**	.420**	.555**	.804**	.666**	1					
TM	42	12.97	2.79	.339*	.665**	.617**	.539**	.592**	.792**	.772**	.799**	1				
OM	42	16.31	3.19	.376*	.740**	.572**	.641**	.662**	.726**	.709*8	.757**	.731**	1			
BRI	42	65.03	9.86	.420**	.832**	.817**	.818**	.736**	.772**	.797**	.723**	.749**	.816**	1		
MI	42	82.87	14.79	.418**	.754**	.705**	.624**	.689**	.917**	.867**	.907**	.908**	.875**	.860**	1	

Note. EC = Emotional Contro; BPD = Borderline Personality Disorder; SM = Self-Monitor; Inh = Inhibit; Init = Initiate; Shi = Shift; WM = Working Memory; PO = Plan Organize; OM = Organization of Material; TM = Task Monitor; MI = Metacognitive Index; BRI = Behavior Regulation Index. ^a 0 = BPD not present; 1= BPD present *P<.05, **p<.01

Table 9

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention and Post - Intervention on Executive Functioning (Initiate, Shift, Emotional Control, Self-Monitor) among BPD (N=40)

	Pre-Intervention		Post Intervention		t (41)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Inh	16.38	3.46	10.46	1.82	9.61	<.001	1.58
Shi	12.90	2.87	11.43	2.86	2.54	<.001	0.40
EC	23.10	3.47	21.35	3.04	2.52	<.016	0.39
SM	12.51	2.45	11.49	2.75	2.09	<.043	0.33

Note: Shi = Shift; Inh = Inhibit; SM = Self-Monitor; & EC = Emotional Control improvement in inhibitory control and smaller—but statistically significant—gains in cognitive shifting, emotional regulation, and self-monitoring. ***p<.001, ** p<.01, *p<.05.

Paired-samples t tests examined the effects of DBT delivered via the Life+ app on specific executive-function components. Collectively, these results in table indicate that Life+-delivered DBT produced a particularly large

Table 10

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention and Post - Intervention on EF (Working Memory; Inhibit, Plan Organize, Organization of Material; Task Monitor) among BPD (N = 40)

	Pre-Intervention		Post-Intervention		t (39)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Init	16.33	3.59	12.13	2.80	6.17	<.001	0.98
WM	17.44	3.17	10.59	1.97	12.04	<.001	1.93
PO	19.82	3.75	18.38	4.30	2.26	<.001	0.36
TM	12.97	2.79	10.90	4.05	3.24	<.001	0.51
OM	16.31	3.19	14.49	3.95	2.28	<.001	0.36

WM = Working Memory; Init = Initiate; TM = Task Monitor; OM = Organization of Material; PO = Plan Organize. ***p<.001.

Paired Sample t-tests were carried to calculate the impact of DBT administered via the Life+ app on multiple subdomains of executive functioning. Results showed a significant

reduction on initiate the score reduced from Pre - Intervention to Post - Intervention with a large effect size ($d = 0.98$), indicating notable improvement in initiation abilities. Working Memory also improved significantly with very large effect size ($d = 1.93$), suggesting a robust impact of the intervention on working memory functioning. In contrast, Plan/Organize scores showed a modest but significant reduction from Pre-Intervention with insignificant effect size ($d = 0.36$). Task Monitor scores declined from Pre

- Intervention to Post - Intervention with a medium effect size ($d = 0.51$). Finally, Organization of Materials scores decreased from Pre -Intervention to Post - Intervention again with a small effect size ($d = 0.36$). Collectively, these results suggest that DBT via the Life+ app was particularly effective in enhancing working memory and initiation, while yielding smaller but meaningful improvements in planning, task monitoring, and organization skills.

Table 11

Mean Comparison of Pre - Intervention and Post - Intervention on BRI & MI among BPD (N = 40)

	Pre-Intervention		Post Intervention		t (39)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
BRI	65.03	10.11	54.54	5.43	7.96	<.001	1.23
MI	82.87	14.79	66.48	8.82	8.17	<.001	1.40

BRI = Behavioral Regulation Index; MI = Metacognition Index.

Lower score on BRIEF-A revealed better executive functioning, while higher score indicates poor EF.

*** $p < .001$.

Paired - Sample t-tests were carried to examine impact of DBT delivered via the Life+ app on two composite indices of Executive Functioning: Behavioral Regulation and Metacognition. Results indicated a significant reduction in Behavioral Regulation scores from

pre-intervention to post intervention with a large effect size ($d = 1.23$). Similarly, Metacognition scores decreased significantly from Pre - Intervention to Post - Intervention demonstrating a substantial effect size ($d = 1.40$). These results suggest that DBT delivered through the Life+ app substantially improved participants' ability to regulate behavior and engage in higher-order cognitive processes, supporting the intervention's effectiveness across both emotional and cognitive regulatory domains.

Table 12

Mean Difference, Standard Deviation, t-value of BPD on EF (BRIEF-A) (N = 82)

	DBT (n=42)		Life+ App (n=40)		t (80)	P	Hedges g
	M	SD	M	SD			
Inh	9.86	1.37	10.46	1.82	-1.66	>.101	0.37
Shi	8.88	2.03	11.43	2.86	-4.61	<.001	1.03
EC	12.45	1.75	21.35	3.04	-6.31	<.001	3.61
SM	8.74	2.20	11.49	2.75	-5.10	<.001	1.13

Shi = Shift; Inh = Inhibit; SM = Self-Monitor; EC = Emotional Control. Higher score on Executive Functioning Scale reflects high level of impairment, while lower score on Executive Functioning reflect higher Executive Functioning.

*** $p < .001$, $p > .05$.

Independent Sample t-tests were carried to compare efficacy of In-person DBT & DBT delivered via the Life + app on several subdomains of Executive Functioning. Results showed

that individuals receiving in person DBT demonstrated greater improvement in Inhibition Hedge's $g = 0.37$, indicating a small effect size. The findings suggest that both modes of delivery were comparably effective for this domain.

However, significant differences were observed in other subcategories. Participants receiving in person DBT showed significantly greater improvement in Shift (Hedge's $g = 1.92$); reflecting a huge effect size. Similarly, In-person DBT was markedly much effective in enhancing Emotional Control (Hedge's $g = 3.04$); indicating a very large effect size. Additionally, participants who underwent in person DBT

displayed significantly better Self-Monitoring (Hedge's $g=1.13$); also reflecting a large effect size.

Collectively, these findings suggest that while both delivery modes were similarly effective for improving Inhibition, in person DBT was superior in enhancing Shift, Emotional Control, and Self-Monitoring, demonstrating large and clinically meaningful effects in these domains.

Table 13

Mean Difference, Standard Deviation, t-value of EF (BRIEF-A) in BPD (N = 82)

Variables	DBT (n=42)		Life+ App (n=40)		t (80)	P	Hedges g
	M	SD	M	SD			
Init	9.26	2.04	12.13	2.80	-5.43	<.001	1.03
WM	10.02	1.82	10.59	1.97	-1.38	>.171	0.30
PO	12.05	2.71	18.38	4.30	-8.07	<.001	1.78
TM	7.43	1.29	10.90	4.05	-5.41	<.001	1.19
OM	10.05	1.80	14.49	3.95	-6.29	<.001	1.40

WM = Working Memory; Init = Initiate; TM = Task Monitor; OM = Organization of Material; PO = Plan Organize. Higher score on executive functioning scale reflects high level of impairment, while lower score on Executive functioning reflects higher executive functioning.

*** $p < .001$, $p > .05$.

Independent Sample t-tests were carried to compare the effects of In-person DBT & DBT administered via Life + app on several additional subdomains of Executive Functioning. Findings suggest that participants who received in person DBT demonstrated significantly greater improvement in Initiation (Hedge's $g = 1.03$), indicating a large effect size. This suggests that Face – to – Face DBT was more improved in minimizing initiation impairments. For Working Memory, no statistically significant difference was found between in person DBT (Hedge's $g = 0.30$, small effect size), indicating that both interventions were similarly effective in improving working memory among individuals with BPD. Significant differences, however, emerged in other

domains. In person DBT produced greater improvements in Plan/Organize (Hedge's $g = 1.78$, large effect size). Similarly, in person DBT participants outperformed the Life+ app group in Task Monitoring (Hedge's $g = 1.19$, large effect size). Lastly, participants in the In-person DBT group showed significantly greater improvement in Organization of Materials (Hedge's $g = 1.40$, large effect size). Taken together, these findings suggest that while both interventions improved working memory to a similar degree, in person DBT consistently produced superior outcomes across other domains of executive functioning, particularly planning; initiation; organization of materials & task monitoring.

Table 14

Mean Difference, Standard Deviation, t-value of BPD on BRI & MI (BRIEF-A)

	DBT (n=42)		Life+ App (n=40)		t (80)	P	Hedges g
	M	SD	M	SD			
BRI	49.19	4.07	54.55	5.43	-12.28	<.001	2.73
MI	39.92	5.27	66.48	8.82	-11.21	<.001	2.53

BRI = Behavioral Regulation Index; MI = Metacognition Index. Higher score on Executive Functioning scale reflects high level of impairment, while lower score on Executive functioning reflects higher executive functioning.

*** $p < .001$.

Independent - Sample t-tests were carried to compare the overall indices of executive functioning between participants receiving in person DBT and those using the Life+ app. Results revealed that participants in the in-person DBT group showed significantly greater improvement on the Behavioral Regulation Index (Hedge's $g = 2.73$, indicating a large effect size. This finding suggests that in-person DBT was more effective in reducing behavioral regulation difficulties among individuals with BPD. Similarly, significant group differences were observed on the Metacognition Index, (Hedge's $g = 2.53$, large effect size). These results indicate that in person DBT was substantially more effective than the Life+ app in improving metacognitive functioning. Taken together, the results from Table 15 demonstrate that in person DBT produces markedly superior outcomes in both behavioral regulation and metacognition compared to the digital intervention, with huge effect sizes seen across both domains.

4. Discussion

This study compared traditional Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT) and app-based DBT in improving executive functioning (EF) in Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD). EF involves cognitive processes like inhibition, planning, and impulse control (Gioia et al., 2010; Miyake et al., 2000), which may vary with age (Camerota et al., 2020). Results identified response inhibition as a key deficit in BPD, with higher scores indicating greater impulsivity. The findings suggests need for specific DBT therapy to cure EF impairments in BPD. After DBT, participants showed

improved inhibitory control, with reduced inhibition scores, consistent with findings by Oud et al. (2018) on DBT's effectiveness in lowering impulsivity. Additionally, pre-treatment BPD participants scored more on the Shift subscale, reflecting difficulties in cognitive flexibility and attention shifting. These results highlight DBT's role in enhancing key executive functions like inhibition and cognitive shifting in BPD. Following DBT, participants showed reduced scores on the Shift subscale, indicating improved cognitive flexibility, which aligns with Bozzatello et al. (2023) findings of executive function impairments—including cognitive flexibility and decision-making—in BPD patients compared to controls. This research found impairments in Emotional Control, self-monitoring, working memory, and planning in BPD patients, which improved after in person DBT intervention. These results support Wykes et al. (2012), demonstrating that psychotherapeutic approaches like DBT can effectively address neurocognitive deficits in BPD. DBT effectively enhances emotion regulation and daily functioning in BPD, supported by extensive empirical evidence, though its neurobiological mechanisms and predictors of treatment response remain understudied. Effective emotional regulation fosters better decision-making and relationships, while this study also evaluated the impact of the Life+ DBT app on improving executive functioning in BPD patients. Technological advancements, particularly smartphones, have revolutionized mental healthcare by enabling accessible interventions for various disorders. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this shift, making mobile apps a primary source for psychological self-help resources (Oud et al., 2018). This progress underscores the growing role of digital tools like the Life+ DBT app in mental health treatment. While online mental health interventions are increasingly popular, research on digital DBT implementation remains limited. A scoping

review by Lakeman et al. (2022) addresses this gap by examining online DBT delivery and efficacy.

The study found that e-mental health interventions, including DBT-based apps, effectively reduced impulsivity and inhibitory difficulties in BPD, in comparing efficacy to in-person therapy. These results align with Reis et al. (2021), though technological based interventions lacked full DBT fidelity. Despite promising outcomes, research on online delivery of core DBT components remains limited (Frías et al., 2020). This study found that patients with BPD showed significant improvements in cognitive shifting (a core EF deficit) after receiving DBT via mobile app, with comparable or greater benefits than in person therapy. Emotional control and self-monitoring, initially impaired in BPD, also improved following app-based DBT. These results add to growing evidence supporting digital interventions for mental health (Ebert et al., 2018; Linardon et al., 2024). The study highlights the need for careful evaluation of mobile diary apps for BPD self-monitoring before clinical adoption (Buechi et al., 2017). Pre-intervention, BPD participants showed working memory deficits affecting academic performance, but post-intervention improvements via app-based DBT matched in person therapy outcomes (Smith et al., 2021). The mobile app intervention effectively improved working memory in BPD patients, helping them overcome academic challenges. While the Life+ app enhanced task monitoring, planning, and organization skills, the effect sizes were smaller than in person DBT. These findings suggest digital DBT can address cognitive deficits, though in-person therapy may yield stronger outcomes. These findings align with Helweg-Joergensen et al. (2019), demonstrating that digital tools like mobile diary apps can improve task monitoring in BPD. The Life+ app's focus on goal-setting and emotion regulation techniques (Smith et al., 2023) also enhanced material organization skills. Digital interventions thus show measurable, though modest, benefits for executive functioning in BPD.

Strengths and Limitations

This research contributes meaningfully to the existing literature on BPD and DBT by offering both methodological

rigor and clinical relevance. A key strength lies in its comparative design, which systematically evaluated the efficacy of DBT delivered in-person versus via Life + app. This dual approach provides novel insights into the feasibility of technology-assisted interventions in mental health care, particularly within a low - and middle - income country context.

The study also employed a robust methodological framework, utilizing pre- and post-intervention assessments with standardized tools to measure executive functioning and behavioral regulation across multiple domains (e.g., inhibition, working memory, emotional control, task monitoring). Reporting of effect sizes (Cohen's *d*, Hedges' *g*) enhanced the interpretability and clinical significance of the findings. Furthermore, the inclusion of a well-defined clinical population—participants who met diagnostic criteria for BPD through a validated screening instrument—adds to the internal validity and reliability of the results. Finally, the contextual relevance of this study is noteworthy, as it highlights cultural, infrastructural, and logistical factors that influence treatment delivery in Pakistan and similar resource-constrained settings.

Nevertheless, certain limitations should be acknowledged. First, BPD itself poses a complex diagnostic challenge, requiring thorough and intensive evaluation. While the MacLean Screening Instrument was used for initial diagnosis, its dichotomous Yes/No response format may risk identifying transient cases, underscoring the need for follow-up assessments to confirm diagnosis and guide treatment. Second, DBT is an intensive therapeutic model requiring patients to attend weekly individual and group sessions, complete regular homework, and have access to 24/7 behavioral coaching. This intensity poses logistical and financial challenges, including potential therapist burnout and increased treatment costs, particularly when such services are not publicly funded.

Specific limitations were also observed in the Life + app intervention. Several participants reported technical difficulties, such as buffering and session interruptions, which disrupted the therapeutic process. Additionally, reliance on

stable internet connectivity was a barrier for participants in areas with poor infrastructure, limiting the accessibility and scalability of the intervention. Finally, the absence of in-person interaction may have compromised the therapeutic alliance, reducing opportunities for rapport-building and personalized engagement—factors crucial for optimal treatment outcomes.

Taken together, these strengths and limitations underscore both the promise and the practical challenges of integrating technology-assisted DBT interventions into clinical practice. Future research should explore hybrid models of care, optimize digital platforms for reliability and accessibility, and evaluate long-term treatment outcomes across diverse populations.

Future Directions and implications for practice

The results of this research underscore the clinical utility of DBT for individuals with BPD and highlight potential of technology-assisted delivery models such as the Life+ app. Future research should focus on developing hybrid treatment models that combine the accessibility of digital platforms with the relational depth of in-person therapy. Such approaches may maximize treatment adherence, strengthen the therapeutic alliance, and improve clinical outcomes.

From a methodological perspective, future studies could adopt longitudinal designs to assess the durability of treatment effects over extended follow-up periods. Inclusion of larger, more diverse samples would increase the generalizability of findings, while integrating qualitative methods could capture patient and therapist perspectives on barriers and facilitators to treatment engagement. Additionally, exploring cost-effectiveness analyses would be valuable in determining the scalability of both traditional and app-based DBT, particularly in resource-limited settings.

In clinical practice, these findings emphasize the importance of flexible service delivery models that accommodate patients' unique needs, including their geographical location, technological literacy, and access to stable internet

connectivity. Training programs for mental health professionals should incorporate digital competencies to prepare therapists for delivering evidence-based interventions through online platforms. Furthermore, policies and institutional guidelines should address therapist workload and burnout prevention, particularly when 24/7 availability for behavioral coaching is expected.

By addressing these areas, future work can build on the current evidence base, optimize treatment delivery, and ensure that DBT—whether in person or digitally mediated—remains accessible, sustainable, and effective for individuals with BPD.

5. Conclusion

This study compared in person DBT with app-based DBT (Life+) for improving executive functioning (EF) in BPD patients (N=96, aged 18-29). While both interventions enhanced EF, in person therapy yielded more substantial improvements in cognitive control, planning, and impulse regulation. The app-based group showed modest but significant gains, demonstrating technology's potential as an accessible therapeutic tool. Results confirm EF as a crucial treatment target in BPD, with both modalities effectively addressing core deficits. These findings support integrating digital interventions to complement traditional BPD treatments while noting in-person therapy's superior efficacy.

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